

ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCIES REQUIRED BY TECHNICAL EDUCATION GRADUATES UPON GRADUATION FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN RIVERS STATE

BY

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Abstract

The study sought to identify entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates for sustainable economic development in Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Entrepreneurial Competencies Required by Technical Education Graduates for Sustainable Economic Development Questionnaire” (ECTEGQ). The result of the study revealed that entrepreneurial competencies for sustainable economic development were required by technical education graduates in Rivers State. It was therefore recommended among others that technology education institutions and department should ensure that they establish and maintain effective linkage with business and industries as well as chambers of commerce to gain from their wealth of experiences and resources in operating small and medium ventures upon their graduation, adequate fund should be made available for entrepreneurship education programme in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial, competencies, graduates, sustainable, economic development.*

Introduction

Technical education is the training programme that teaches individual knowledge, skills and mindsets designed to make them more productive in a designated occupation or broader cluster of occupation. According to Steven and Miller (2021) technical education programme any where in the world over is aimed at preparing and providing the learner with employable skills. Similarly, technical education according to Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) is the aspect of education that leads to the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge. Ezeobi and Achebe (2022) stated that technical education is the training of technical oriented personnel who are to be the initiators facilitators and implementers of

technological development of a nation, through adequate training of its citizenry on the need to be technologically literate leading to self-reliance and sustainability.

According to Agwi and Okpara (2023) programme in technical education such as Bachelor Degree in Technology (Education), Nigeria Certificate in Education and others was designed to equip students with skills, values, attitude and related knowledge in technology. In the view of Zamani and Umaru (2021) technology education programme is designed to equip technology education graduates with skills in instruction and technical areas of technology as to enable them impact same to learners in schools. Ile and Ukachukwu cited in Darigo and Tambari

(2021) stressed that in most cases, students that graduated from technical education programmes are without the requisite entrepreneurial competencies that will lead them to economic development.

Economic development is the development of economic wealth of countries, regions or communities for the well-being of their inhabitants. According to Jantez (2023) economic development are efforts that seek to improve the economic well-being and quality of life for a community by creating and retaining jobs and supporting or growing incomes and the revenue base. Economic development of technical education graduates is therefore the change in the economic status of the individuals from substance to the level of affluence. Students are not rich when they depend on their parents/guardians for financial support. The situation worsens after graduation when nobody will support them financially. These individuals will now depend on their ingenuity and creativity to improve their financial status. The opportunity they have is the entrepreneurial competency possessed by them. This will go a long way in sustaining their economic base making them self-reliant and improve the economy of the nation.

According to Wada and Chinda (2022) entrepreneurship is the application of enterprise skills specifically to creating and growing organizations in order to identify and build on opportunities. Ukachukwu cited in Johnson and Uwem (2021) identified entrepreneurship as a means of providing employment and income generation in the country and a panacea to poverty reduction

and pathetic unemployment situation. According to Ugwuoha and Ekwem (2022) entrepreneurship prepares people especially youths to be responsible enterprising individuals who will become entrepreneurs, or entrepreneurial thinkers that will contribute to economic development and sustainable communities. Uzundu and Kamadu (2023) stated that entrepreneurship is the process of bringing together creative and innovative ideas and combining them with management and organizational skills in order to combine people and money, and thereby create wealth. Umar and Atahiru (2022) stated that entrepreneurship is not based on theory, instead students are trained in practical experiences where they will have an opportunity to take-off risk, manage the results and learn from the outcomes. To achieve this, Kolawale and Ibrahim (2023) suggested that educational institutions should establish small business ventures and linkage with experienced entrepreneurs, industries and government establishment for support. Similarly, Okon and Udo (2021) suggested that experienced entrepreneurs and resource persons from industries should be invited from time to time to encourage and inculcate entrepreneurship in student that are undergoing training in tertiary institutions. Also involving the private sector and government establishment in the teaching of entrepreneurship would provide more realistic information, materials and experience to both students and educators. Ikpe and Iwu (2019) indicated that the practical ways of teaching entrepreneurship skills should include demonstration, field trip, project, apprenticeship, industrial training and simulation method.

However, Walter (2019) started that entrepreneurship involves the acquisition of practical knowledge and skill needed by students to function in their own business upon their graduation from school. Onyenwoke (2020) stated that entrepreneurship involves the acquisition of business skills that an individual required upon graduation from school to function effectively in generating money for an organization. This requires that the individual must be competent. Ezekwesiri cited in Chukwuma(2019) stated that to be competent means that the individual has acquired the knowledge, skill and attitude required in order to perform successfully at a specified proficiency level in a given work. Entrepreneurial competencies required for sustainable economic development is the knowledge, skills and attitudes to perform successfully at specified proficiency level in a given work (Adamu, 2023).

Entrepreneurial competencies for sustainable economic development refers to the knowledge, skills and attitudes that an individual such as technical education graduates, requires in order to set up their own private business, and become self-employed and also be able to employ others that will work for them. Training in entrepreneurship according to Peters and Rubben (2020) involves the extent to which entrepreneurs are dynamic, flexible, self-regulating and engaged in the process of generating multiple decision framework which will focus on generating process of changes in the environment. It also involves the establishment of mechanisms that identify potential opportunities. Technical education graduates can be trained to function

effectively in any business opportunities. According to Ogumba and Bread (2022) entrepreneurship competencies that technical education graduates required for subsumable economic development include; managerial abilities and risk management competences, creative thinking and innovation competencies, technical consultation and interview competencies, leadership development competencies, technical planning and organization strategies. Danladi and Kola (2021) posited that entrepreneurial competencies that technology education graduates who majored in any of the technology related trades required for entrepreneurial success upon graduation are, risk taking, networking, integrity, conceptual thinking, strategic thinking, commercial aptitude, and customer sensitivity. The authors further stated that any individual during the period of training at the tertiary institution who acquired all the stated competencies stands the chance to succeed in business upon graduation.

Ezekwe and Osadebe (2020) stated that despite the tremendous of growth in entrepreneurship education around the world Nigeria inclusive, that many challenges are been faced by students who are undergoing entrepreneurship education training in various higher institutions which had tend to constrain the entrepreneurial competencies that these students requires for sustainable economic development upon their graduation. According to Madumere and Osuaka (2023) challenges of entrepreneurship education that constrain students entrepreneurship competencies that they require during the periods of their training in the school includes;

poor linkage with business, industries, government and non-governmental organizations, lack of strong government policy and support, inadequate qualified staff with capacity of entrepreneurship education and training, poor management and maintenance of available resources, inadequate funding, absence of curricular capacity to support entrepreneurship training, inadequate equipments facilities and infrastructure and inadequate information and materials on entrepreneurship education.

Several studies such as (Faruk, 2021, Galadima and Zubairo, 2023; Nwokolo, 2028) indicated that in order to achieve viable entrepreneurship education programme that will enhance sustainable economic development in Nigeria, that there is need to adopt an effective strategies that will help to tackle challenges that tends to constrain entrepreneurship education programme as offered in Nigerian higher institutions. According to Hampton (2022) strategies that must be adopted in Nigeria in order to achieve viable entrepreneurship education programme in all the tertiary institutions include; establishment of school-based enterprise where students will identify potential business plan, establish an enterprise college aimed at fostering the specific skills sets required for entrepreneurship to serve as skill education center for the youths, invest local, public and private funds on apprenticeship programme, establish a small business school were interested students and community members can participate.

This study adopts McClellands competency-based theory as its theoretical foundation, complemented by the sustainable

development framework. By identifying the competencies that enable technical graduates to become successful entrepreneurs.

Statement of the Problem

The technical education system in Rivers State produces a sustainable number of graduates each year, yet a persistent and widening gap exists between the skills acquired during training and the competencies demanded by the labour market. Despite government investments in vocational and technical programmes Eduga and Ike (2023) observed that unemployment among technical graduates remain high-approximately 38% in 2024 and many employers report that graduates lack essential entrepreneurial abilities such as opportunity identification, risk management and business planning (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013).

This mismatch has contributed to low rates of new venture creation, under utilization of human capital and hinders the state goal of achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 8 and 9). Consequently, there is an urgent need to identify the specific entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates to bridge the training employability divide and foster sustainable economic growth in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Identify entrepreneurial competencies

required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State.

2. Identify challenges constraining entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State.
3. Identify strategies that are needed to be adopted in order to tackle challenges constraining entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State?
2. What are the challenges constraining entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State?
3. What are the strategies that are needed to be adopted in order to tackle challenges constraining entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State?

Design of the Study

The study adopted a descriptive survey

research design. According to Bell and Gall cited in Agwi and Njoku (2023) descriptive survey design is aimed at or describing in a systematic manner, the characteristic feature or fact about a given population.

Population

The population of the study was seventy eight (78) lecturers made up of 35 lecturers from F.C.E. (T) Omoku, 20 lecturers from Rivers State University, Port Harcourt and 23 lecturers from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The entire population was used for collection of data for the study as the population size was rather manageable.

Development of Research Instrument

The instrument used for data collection was a 40-item questionnaire titled “Entrepreneurial Competencies required by Technical Education Graduates for Sustainable Economic Development Questionnaire” (ECTEQ). The response category of the instrument adopted four (4) point rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

Validity of the Instrument

The rating scale was submitted to three experts in Industrial Technology Education Department, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Their suggestions were used in the modification of the statements of the rating scale.

Reliability of the Instrument

To ascertain the reliability of the instrument it

was administered on 15 lecturers who were not part of the study. Cronbach alpha reliability technique was used to determine the internal consistency of the items of the questionnaire. The reliability co-efficient obtained was 0.95.

Administration of the Instrument

A total of 78 copies of the instrument were administered to the respondents directly by the researchers with the help of five research assistants. The total number of the instrument retrieved after two weeks was 76 copies and

was used for data analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

In answering the research question a cut-off point 2.50 was used in taking decision. Any item with a mean rating of 2.50 and above were taken as required while any item whose weighted mean is below 2.50 was regarded as not required. An item that attracted an average of 2.50 and above was considered as an agreement while an item below 2.50 were considered as disagreement.

Results

The results of the study are presented in Tables 1-3 in line with the research questions.

Research Question1: What are the entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation Responses on Entrepreneurial Competencies Required by Technical Education Graduates upon Graduation for Sustainable Economic Development in Rivers State

N= 76				
	Entrepreneurial Competencies Required	X	SD	Remark
1.	Assess management and control strategies	3.21	0.85	Required
2.	Office organization and administrative strategies	3.01	0.78	Required
3.	Technical co-ordination and control strategies for office	2.65	0.69	Required
4.	Service and system			
5.	Problem solving and decision making competencies	2.89	0.75	Required
6.	Technical consultation and interview competencies	2.72	0.70	Required
7.	Computer appreciation and application competencies	2.80	0.73	Required
8.	Business law and risk protection competencies	3.20	0.83	Required
9.	Leadership development competencies	3.18	0.80	Required
10.	Conflict/crisis management and application competencies	2.59	0.63	Required
11.	Small business management competencies	2.92	0.63	Required
12.	Interpersonal and industrial related competencies	2.72	0.64	Required

13. Product development strategies	2.81	0.65	Required
14. Creative thinking and innovative competencies	3.00	0.76	Required
15. Time management competencies	3.15	0.79	Required
16. Managerial ability and risk management competencies	3.19	0.81	Required
Technical planning and organization strategies	2.84	0.63	Required

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The data in Table 1: revealed that technical education graduates upon graduation required all the 16 entrepreneurial competencies for sustainable economic development in Rivers State. Mean scores for each of the 16 items exceeded 2.50 which is

the cut-off point. The entrepreneurial competencies had their standard deviation ranged from 0.63 to 0.83. This indicated that the respondents were close to one another in their opinion and were also not too far away from the mean.

Research Question 2: What are the challenges constraining entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State.

Table 2: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation Responses on Challenges Constraining Entrepreneurial Competencies Required by Technical Education Graduates upon Graduation for Sustainable Economic Development in Rivers State.

		N=76		
Entrepreneurial Competencies Required		X	SD	Remark
17.	Inadequate information and materials for entrepreneurship Education.	3.05	0.81	Agree
18.	Poor linkage with business, industries, government and organizations	2.89	0.72	Agree
19.	Inadequate qualified staff with capacity in entrepreneurship education and training	2.95	0.74	Agree
20.	Lack of model small business establishment and laboratories in the institutions for practice	2.89	0.72	Agree
21.	Poor organization and supervision of student industrial work experiences scheme.	3.06	0.82	Agree
22.	Lack of incentives to motivate the educators and instructors	3.01	0.80	Agree
23.	Poor management and maintenance of available resource in the training institutions	3.10	0.85	Agree
24.	Inadequate research and development on entrepreneurship	2.83	0.71	Agree
25.	Lack of skill manpower to train students in entrepreneurship	3.21	0.87	Agree
26.	Poor state of infrastructure in training institutions	3.12	0.83	Agree
27.	Inadequate or outright lack of funding	2.75	0.70	Agree
28.	Absence of curricula capacity to support the training	3.28	0.91	Agree

29. Lack of strong government policy and support	3.22	0.88	Agree
30. Hasty preparation for entrepreneurship programme	3.87	0.71	Agree
Average Mean/SD	2.98	0.79	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The data in Table 2 revealed the challenges constraining entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State had their mean ranged from 2.75 to 3.28. Mean scores for each of the 14 items exceeded the 2.50 cut-off point. The respondents agreed on the 14 items as challenges constraining

entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development. The standard deviation ranged from 0.70 to 0.91. This indicated that the respondents were close to one another in their opinion and were also not too far away from the mean.

Research Questions 3: what are the strategies that are needed to be adopted in order to tackle challenges constraining entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State.

Table 3: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation on Strategies to be Adopted in order to tackle Challenges Constraining Entrepreneurial Competencies Required by Technical Education Graduates upon Graduation for Sustainable Economic Development.

Strategies	N= 76		Remark
	X	SD	
31. Organizing regular workshop/seminars	3.10	0.87	Agree
32. Provide small business schools where interested students and Community member can participate	3.05	0.78	Agree
33. Develop entrepreneurship internship programmes matching Students with locally successful entrepreneurship to serve as skill acquisition centres for the youths	2.95	0.76	Agree
34. Creating an economic friendly political environment	2.68	0.73	Agree
35. Improving on the government taxation on small scale business	3.24	0.92	Agree
36. Intensive monitoring of entrepreneurship education projects By economic reform implementers	3.23	0.90	Agree
37. Government representatives should disburse monies meant For entrepreneurs judiciously and not to divert it to their Private account	3.07	0.80	Agree
38. Training and retraining of teachers/lecturer of Entrepreneurship education periodically	2.87	0.75	Agree
39. Creation of market for exhibition and sale of locally made goods	3.13	0.89	Agree

40. Government should establish an enterprise college aimed at fostering the specific skills required by entrepreneurship	3.09	0.83	Agree
Average Mean/SD	3.05	0.82	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Data in Table 3 revealed that strategies that are needed to be adopted in order to tackle challenges constraining entrepreneurship competencies required by technical education graduates had their mean ranged from 2.68 to 3.24. Mean scores for each of the 10 items exceeded the 2.50 cut-off point. The respondents agreed on all the 10 items as strategies to be adopted in order to tackle challenges constraining entrepreneurship competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State. The standard deviation ranged from 0.73 to 0.92. This indicated that the respondents were close to one another in their opinion and were not too far away from the mean.

Findings of the Study

The following are the findings of the study:

1. Sixteen entrepreneurial competencies were identified by technology educators as entrepreneurial competencies that are required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State
2. Fourteen challenges were identified by technology educators as major challenges constraining entrepreneurial competencies that are required by technical education graduates upon their graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State.

3. Ten strategies were identified by technology educators as strategies that are needed to be adopted in order to improve on the quality of entrepreneurial competencies that are required by technical education graduates upon their graduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State.

Discussion

Discussion of the findings of the study were made according to the research questions posed in the study.

Entrepreneurial Competencies Required by Technical Education Graduates Upon Graduation for Sustainable Economic Development in Rivers State.

The findings from Table 1 revealed that technical education graduates required all the 16 entrepreneurial competencies identified for sustainable economic development in Rivers State. These findings are in consonance with many related article, reports and literature. Ogumba and Bread (23022) stated that entrepreneurial competencies that technical education graduates required for sustainable economic development include, managerial abilities and risk management competencies, creative thinking and innovative competencies, technical consultation and interview competencies, leadership development competencies, technical planning and organization strategies. The finding from Table 1 were also in consonance with the study by Danladi

and Kola (2021) that entrepreneurial competencies that technology education graduates who major edinary of the technology related trades required for entrepreneurial success upon graduation are, risk taking, networking, integrity, conceptual thinking, strategic thinking, commercial aptitude, and customer sensitivity. The authors furthers stated that any individual during the period of training at the tertiary institution who acquired all the stated competencies through entrepreneurship education stands the chance to succeed in business upon graduation from school. This implies that technical education graduated should focus on tasks to be accomplished no matter what happens. They should be committed to achieve knowledge, skills and attitude that will enable them to succeed upon graduation.

Challenges Constraining Entrepreneurial Competencies Required by Technical Education Graduates upon Graduation for Sustainable Economic Development in River State

The findings from Table 2 revealed that all the 14 challenges of entrepreneurial competencies identified were agreed as constraints for technical education graduates upon their graduation for sustainable economic development in Nigeria. This finding is in line with Ezekwe and Osadebe (2020) that despite the tremendous of growth in entrepreneurship education around the world Nigeria inclusive, that many challenges are been faced by students' who are undergoing entrepreneurship education training in various higher institutions which had tend to constrain their entrepreneurial

competencies that these students requires for sustainable economic development. The finding from Table 2 were also in agreement with Madumere and Osuaka (2023) who pointed out challenges of entrepreneurship education that constrain students entrepreneurial competencies that they require during the period of their training in the school to include; low level funding for training, shortage of qualified manpower and poor management of the available resources. The result validated the statement of Nwokolo (2018) that entrepreneurship education must be included in tertiary institutions curricula so that the educators must be adequately trained and motivated with adequate incentives, instructional resources and finding to teach students entrepreneurship competences with creativity and innovations.

Strategies that are needed to be adopted in order to tackle challenges constraining entrepreneurialcompetenciesrequiredbytechnicaleducationgraduatesupongraduation for sustainable economic development in Rivers State.

The finding from Table 3 revealed that all the 10 strategies needed to be adopted in order to tackle challenges constraining entrepreneurial competencies required by technical education graduates upon graduation for sustainable economic development were agreed by technology educators as strategies that are needed to be adopted for effective entrepreneurship education programme. The finding is in line with (Nwokolo, 2018; Faruk, 2021 and Galachma, 2023) that in order to achieve viable entrepreneurship education programme that will enhance sustainable economic development in Nigeria, that there is need to adopted an effective strategies that

will help to tackle challenges that tends to constrain entrepreneurship education programme as offered in Nigerian higher institutions. The finding in Table 3 were also in agreement with Hampton (2022) who pointed out that strategies that must be adopted in Nigeria in order to achieve viable entrepreneurship education programme include; establishment of school-based enterprise where students will identify potential business plan, establish an enterprise college aimed fostering the specific skills sets required for entrepreneurship to serve as skill education center for the youths, establish a small business school where interested students and community members can participate. This implies that to achieve the objective of an effective entrepreneurship education programme that will ensure sustainable economic development in Nigeria that government at all levels should ensure to invest on entrepreneurship education programme. This is the sure way of meeting the sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

Conclusion

At this period of economic challenges in Nigeria, entrepreneurial competencies development programme is an effective training programme that can develop technical education graduates by installing and preserving entrepreneurial climate in Nigeria to boost their economic status. However, developing entrepreneurship competencies in technical education is essential for tackling youth unemployment and promoting innovative driven economic growth in Rivers State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. Technical education graduates should possess entrepreneurial competencies in order to secure a job and create job opportunity for others and reduce unemployment.
2. Adequate fund should be made available for entrepreneurship education programme in Nigerian tertiary institutions.
3. Educators of technology education trades should be retrained always for entrepreneurial competencies to ensure that graduates of technology education are well prepared for sustainable economic development.

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